

Supplementary Data

Homogeneous Boroaluminate Xerogels: Synthesis, Characterization, and Catalysis

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Table S1 Reaction summary

Name	Reactions	n (Al) [mmol]	n (B) [mmol]
BOAI-1	$\text{Al}(\text{O}^i\text{Pr})_3 + \text{BCl}_3 \rightarrow \text{Al-O-B} + 3 \text{}^i\text{PrCl}$	19.99	20.01
BOAI-2	$\text{Al}(\text{O}^i\text{Pr})_3 + \text{BCl}_3 \rightarrow \text{Al-O-B} + 3 \text{}^i\text{PrCl}$	20.01	20.00
BOAI-3	$\text{Al}(\text{O}^i\text{Pr})_3 + \text{BCl}_3 \rightarrow \text{Al-O-B} + 3 \text{}^i\text{PrCl}$	20.04	20.01
BOAI-4	$\text{Al}(\text{O}^i\text{Pr})_3 + \text{BCl}_3 \rightarrow \text{Al-O-B} + 3 \text{}^i\text{PrCl}$	20.03	20.01
BOAI-5	$\text{Al}(\text{O}^i\text{Pr})_3 + \text{BCl}_3 \rightarrow \text{Al-O-B} + 3 \text{}^i\text{PrCl}$	20.05	20.02
AIOB-1	$\text{AlCl}_3 + \text{B}(\text{OCH})_3 \rightarrow \text{Al-O-B} + 3 \text{CH}_3\text{Cl}$	15.00	15.00
AIOB-2	$\text{AlCl}_3 + \text{B}(\text{OCH})_3 \rightarrow \text{Al-O-B} + 3 \text{CH}_3\text{Cl}$	15.06	11.25

Table S2 Precursors amounts and their stoichiometric ratios

Xerogel	m (Al) ^a [g]	n (Al) ^b [mmol]	Al:B nominal	Al:B actual ^c	Al:B ICP-OES	m (B) ^d [g]	n (B) ^e [mmol]
BOAI-1	4.083	19.99	1.00	0.999	1.009	18.185	20.01
BOAI-2	4.086	20.01	1.00	1.000	1.020	18.181	20.00
BOAI-3	4.094	20.04	1.00	1.001	1.020	18.190	20.01
BOAI-4	4.091	20.03	1.00	1.001	1.058	18.186	20.01
BOAI-5	4.097	20.05	1.00	1.002	0.995	18.194	20.02
AIOB-1*	2.000	15.00	1.00	1.000	0.939	1.559	15.00
AIOB-2*	2.008	15.06	1.33	1.338	1.326	1.169	11.25

^a mass and ^b molar amount of aluminum precursor (Al(OⁱPr)₃; AlCl₃*) ^c experimental gravimetric measurements, ^d mass and ^e molar amount of a boron precursor (BCl₃ 1M solution; B(OCH₃)₃*).

GC-MS analysis of volatiles

By measuring GC-MS analysis of volatiles from a reaction, the presence of isopropyl chloride, produced by elimination according to Equation 1, was not observed in GC-MS. However, we could easily observe products of Friedel-Crafts alkylation of toluene with isopropyl groups. This is confirmation of the presence of acidic sites in the BOAl-1 to -5 gels. In all cases, there are the following chemicals present:

1-methyl-3-isopropyl benzene (RT 7.49 min, m/z: 133.9; 119.1; 90.8).

1-methyl-2-isopropyl benzene (RT 7.58 min, m/z: 133.9; 119.1; 90.8)

1-methyl-4-isopropyl benzene (RT 7.75 min, m/z: 133.9; 119.1; 90.8)

1-methyl-3,5-bisopropyl benzene (RT 10.04 min, m/z: 176.0; 161.0; 132.9)

NMR spectroscopy

Trimethyl borate

Fig. S1 ¹H NMR spectrum of B(OCH₃)₃ in CDCl₃

Fig. S2 ^{13}C NMR spectrum of $\text{B}(\text{OCH}_3)_3$ in CDCl_3

Thermogravimetry (TG) analysis

Fig. S3 Thermogravimetry (TG) curve of sample BOAI-5 in synthetic air up to 1000 °C (10 °C min⁻¹ ramp) showing all volatile groups to leave at the temperature 600 °C.

Table S3 Residual masses after TG analysis and the calculated values from the degree of condensation DC (%).

Sample	Residual mass _{TG} [%]	Residual mass _{calc} [%]	Degree of condensation [%]
BOAI-1	72.7	71.3	69.8
BOAI-2	75.3	75.0	77.5
BOAI-3	70.1	69.4	71.2
BOAI-4	70.9	71.6	69.2
BOAI-5	72.1	65.7	71.3
AIOB-1	53.4	55.2	53.7
AIOB-2	46.7	49.4	41.1

XRD analysis of samples calcined at different temperatures

Fig. S4 Powder XRD diffractograms of sample BOAI-1 xerogel after calcination to 600 °C (red) and 700 °C with microcrystalline $\text{Al}_4\text{B}_2\text{O}_9$ phase (black).

MAS NMR spectroscopy of calcinated boroaluminate xerogels

BOAI1–5 (See Fig. 5)

Measured at a 500 MHz spectrometer

$\delta^{11}\text{B}$ (reference $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ (−23.9 ppm));

2 ppm; 4-coordinated (tetrahedral) boron

10 ppm; 3-coordinated (incorporated) boron

14 ppm; 3-coordinated (surface/non-incorporated) boron

$\delta^{27}\text{Al}$ ($[\text{Al}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ (0.0 ppm));

0 ppm; 6-coordinated (octahedral) aluminum

30 ppm; 5-coordinated aluminum

60 ppm; 4-coordinated (tetrahedral) aluminum

AlOB-1 before and after catalysis

Measured at a 700 MHz spectrometer

$\delta^{11}\text{B}$ (reference $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ (−23.9 ppm));

2 ppm; 4-coordinated (tetrahedral) boron

20 ppm; 3-coordinated boron

$\delta^{27}\text{Al}$ ($[\text{Al}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ (0.0 ppm));
0 ppm; 6-coordinated (octahedral) aluminum
30 ppm; 5-coordinated aluminum
60 ppm; 4-coordinated (tetrahedral) aluminum

Fig. S6 ^{27}Al MAS NMR spectra of sample AIOB-1 before (black) and after calcination (red)

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis

Fig. S7 XPS spectrum of sample BOAI-1 with labelled peaks of examined orbitals.

Table S4 XPS characterization data of prepared xerogels

Sample	Peak position O 1s [eV]	FWHM O 1s [eV]	Peak position C 1s [eV]	FWHM C 1s [eV]
BOAI-1	532.32	2.54	192.72	1.82
BOAI-2	532.24	2.51	192.74	1.78
BOAI-3	532.17	2.50	192.77	1.84
BOAI-4	532.19	2.53	192.79	1.85
BOAI-5	532.39	2.51	192.79	1.80
AIOB-1	531.86	2.50	192.56	1.69
AIOB-2	531.51	2.74	192.41	1.79
Sample	Peak position B 1s [eV]	FWHM B 1s [eV]	Peak position Al 2p [eV]	FWHM Al 2p [eV]
BOAI-1	532.32	1.94	192.72	1.86
BOAI-2	532.24	1.87	192.74	1.86
BOAI-3	532.17	1.91	192.77	1.87
BOAI-4	532.19	1.91	192.79	1.82
BOAI-5	532.39	1.90	192.79	1.84
AIOB-1	531.86	1.86	192.56	1.78
AIOB-2	531.51	1.91	192.41	1.91

Table S5 Electron microprobe elemental analysis of prepared xerogels with comparison to reference standard oxides. *There is no standard material for boron oxide quantity

Oxide (wt %)				
Sample	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	FeO	Total
BOAI-2	47.77	0.85	0.01	48.63
BOAI-3	42.16	1.41	0.02	43.59
BOAI-4	45.78	1.07	0.02	46.88
Elements (wt %)				
Sample	Al	Cl	O	Total
BOAI-2	25.28	0.00	22.94	48.63
BOAI-3	22.31	0.01	20.60	43.59
BOAI-4	24.23	0.01	22.12	46.88
Elements (at %)*				
Sample	Al	Cl	O	Total
BOAI-2	39.27	0.00	60.12	100.00
BOAI-3	38.67	0.01	60.21	100.00
BOAI-4	39.05	0.02	60.14	100.00

Electron microscopy:

Fig. S8 Electron microprobe analysis image of sample AIOB-4 in wavelength-dispersive mode.

STEM-EDS analysis

Fig. S9 STEM elemental maps of sample BOAI-5; Color code: Orange – Al, Cyan – O. Measured on carbon grid.

Fig. S10 STEM elemental maps of sample AIOB-1; Color code: Orange – Al, Cyan – O. Measured on carbon grid.

Fig. S11 STEM elemental maps of sample AIOB-2; Color code: Orange – Al, Cyan – O. Measured on carbon grid.

Fig. S12 STEM elemental maps of sample AIOB-2; Color code: Red – B, Orange – Al, Cyan – O. Measured on gold grid.

Fig. S13 STEM elemental maps of sample AlOB-2; Color code: Red – B, Orange – Al, Cyan – O. Measured on gold grid.

Fig. S14 EDS spot spectrum showing the Elemental Composition of the sample BOAI-2 with the B K_{α} line designated at approximately 0.18 keV.

SEM analysis

Fig. S15 SEM images of sample AIOB-1 in a secondary electron mode.

Fig. S16 SEM images of sample AIOB-2 in a secondary electron mode.